

SURGICAL TREATMENT OF VARIOUS FORMS OF HYPOSPADIAS

K.N. Ibragimov¹, Yu.M. Akhmedov²

Samarkand State Medical University, Regional Children's Multidisciplinary Medical Center,
Samarkand, Uzbekistan^{1,2}

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Abstract. *Hypospadias is a congenital malformation of the penis, manifested by a ventral and proximal displacement of the external opening of the urethra from the apex of the penis. Hypospadias is one of the most common malformations of the male genital organs. Traditionally, its incidence in the world is given as 1 in 300 newborn boys. Over the past 50 years, there have been many large studies in different parts of the world with conflicting results. The accuracy and reliability of the data obtained are influenced by many factors, so the real prevalence of hypospadias and the tendency for the incidence to increase are difficult to estimate. In order to present such a picture in the future, cooperation between national and international registries is necessary, as well as work on standardization of calculation and information processing methods.*

Keywords: *pediatric urologists, penis, bifid scrotum, cryptorchidism, fetal development.*

Introduction.

Based on the definition of the defect given above, at present, most existing classifications of hypospadias are based on specifying the localization of the dystopic external urethra and do not have a fundamental difference. There is an anterior (distal) form, when the meatus is located on the head of the penis (has some ventral displacement) or the coronal groove; an intermediate (median) form - the meatus is located on the shaft of the penis; a posterior (proximal) form - the meatus is located in the penoscrotal angle, on the scrotum or on the perineum. Congenital anomalies of the penis and urethra are often combined with malformations of other organs of the genitourinary tract. To a greater extent, this applies to the urethra, which can end and open not on the head, but along the entire lower surface of the penis - hypospadias (Kaliteevsky P.F.; 1987). It is often combined with cryptorchidism, bifid scrotum, deformation, torsion of the penis and testicular atrophy. Hypospadias occurs as a result of persistence, i.e., preservation of embryonic structures that normally disappear by a certain period of fetal development. One of the forms of persistence is dysraphia (araphia), i.e., non-closure of the embryonic slit along the entire lower surface of the penis, which was designated by the term hypospadias.

Most pediatric urologists have adopted the division of hypospadias into glans, trunk, and scrotal forms. With this pathology, persistent urination disorders occur from the first days of life of patients. Such children experience voluntary and involuntary urination and develop urinary leakage of the perineum. There are many reports on hypospadias in domestic and foreign literature. The etiology, clinical picture and complications of hypospadias have been studied in detail (Lazyuk G.I. 1980; Lazyuk G.I., Cherstvoy E.D. 1986; Savchenko N.E. 1974; Kravtsova G.I.; Plissan S.O. 1982). However, the increasing incidence of this pathology in our region, unresolved issues of surgical correction of hypospadias depending on the forms of this pathology and the age of sick children, as well as the lack of a unified treatment strategy for various complications of

hypospadias, dictate the need for an even more in-depth and meticulous study of this serious, disabling pathology in boys.

Objective: To improve the results of surgical treatment of various forms of hypospadias in children.

Materials and methods. The work is based on the analysis of the results of examination and surgical treatment of 86 patients aged 3 to 18 years for the period from 2020 to 2025. Inclusion criteria: boys with glans, trunk, and scrotal forms of urethral hypospadias. Methods of examination. Particular importance is attached to the examination of the external genitalia and a detailed assessment of the constituent elements of the defect. It is recommended to determine the size of the penis, the shape of the head and the severity of the scaphoid fossa, the degree of curvature of the cavernous bodies, possible options for rotation of the penis, the identification of coarse scars from previous surgical interventions, and attention is also paid to the size of the foreskin and scrotum

Table 1. Age composition of patients with hypospadias

Age (year)	1-group (capitate)	2- group (stem)	3- group (scrotal)
1-3	19 (45,2%)	12 (46,1%)	10 (55,5%)
4-7	16 (38%)	9 (34,6%)	6 (33,3)
8-11	5 (11,9%)	4 (15,3%)	1 (5,5%)
12-16	2 (4,7%)	1 (3,8%)	1 (5,5%)
Total	42(100%)	26 (100%)	18 (100%)

Table 2. Distribution of patients by clinical forms of hypospadias and the method of surgery.

	Capitate	Stem	Scrotal
Type of operation	MAGPI-23 patients	Urethroplasty-11	Bayrs flap (1-stage)-8
	Khaberlic-19	Ducket-15	Bukkal urethroplastic-10

Results: The analysis of complications in three groups of patients revealed the following: in the main group, complications were found in 5 (11.9%) patients using the MAGPI method. Complications were observed in the form of complete suture divergence in 3 patients; in two of our patients, a month after the operation, narrowing of the external opening of the urethra was observed. Patients operated on using the Haberlik method had complications in two (4.7%) patients, in the form of complete suture divergence. In the second group of patients operated on using the U-shaped urethroplasty method, the incidence of complications was 4 patients (15.3%), three patients had a urethral fistula, and one patient had narrowing of the anastomosis. In the group of patients operated on using the Duckett method, the percentage of complications was 5 (19.2%), one patient had a complete suture divergence, and 4 had a urethral fistula. In patients with the scrotal form, we used a two-stage operation method.

The first stage of the operation consists of excision of the chord, straightening of the penis and transplantation of skin from the foreskin to the body of the penis, for further creation of the urethra. Complications were encountered in three (16.6%) patients, in the form of partial necrosis of the transplanted skin from the foreskin to the body of the penis. The second stage (6 months after the first) was urethroplasty from the transplanted skin. Urethral fistulas were observed in 4 (122.2%) patients.

Stages of the operation.

Conclusion. The MAGPI method using a continuous inverted suture allowed us to achieve a positive result in 84% of cases compared to the Haberlik operation. In the case of the trunk form of hypospadias, the Duckett method we used gave a positive result in 82% of cases, and the U-shaped urethroplasty gave a positive result in 88%. Conclusion: Thus, the most common complications in surgical correction of hypospadias in children are urethral fistulas, partial suture divergence, and cicatricial deformation of the penis. The frequency of complications depends on the form of the defect. Most often, complications occur in children with the trunk and scrotal form, and with the glans form, complications are rare. The success of hypospadias treatment in children depends not only on the correct choice of surgery, but also equally on many nuances of postoperative management - the optimal method of urine diversion, application of a bandage, the use of modern atraumatic suture material and microsurgical instruments significantly improves the results of surgical treatment of hypospadias. According to the results of the study, the trunk form of hypospadias is more common than the proximal forms, in which the dystopic meatus is located in the middle third of the trunk of the penis, is stenotic and causes obstructed urine outflow.

Conclusion. The instrumental and laboratory research methods and surgical treatment methods aimed at correcting this anomaly using transplants of various tissues did not exclude the occurrence of common postoperative complications. Hypospadias correction should be performed at an early age, given the increased ability of tissues to regenerate in young children. Thus, the occurrence of postoperative complications suggests conducting research to develop standardized approaches to assessing hypospadias and choosing a surgical treatment method in order to improve the results of urethroplasty. Taking into account the above, surgical technique, suture material, cutting out flaps, instruments have an important effect

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